

ACHARYA IN THE PRESENT TIMES: AN URGE FOR RETRIEVING CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract

This article will explore the qualities of an Acharya that can be embedded among the present-day teachers. This paper has utilised a qualitative research approach for gathering and analysing information from the existing literature, news articles, renowned blog posts, and in some cases, personal communication. It has been observed that the present-day teachers have deviated from the ethical standards and qualities that this profession entails. This paper will therefore bring to light some of those qualities of an ancient Acharya which can be incorporated among the present-day teachers.

Keywords: *acharya, qualitative research approach, present teachers, teaching profession.*

Introduction:

ॐ असतो मा सद्गमय ।

तमसो मा ज्योतिर्गमय ।

मृत्योर् मा अमृतं गमय ।

ॐ शान्तिः शान्तिः शान्तिः ॥

Om Asato Maa Sad-Gamaya |

Tamaso Maa Jyotir-Gamaya |

Mrtyor-Maa Amrtam Gamaya |

Om Shaantih Shaantih Shaantih ||

Om Asato maa Sadgamaya is a Shanti Mantra (Mantra of Peace), it is taken from Brihadaranyaka Upanishads (1.3.28). What this verse simply means is "Om, lead us from Unreality (of Transitory Existence) to the Reality (of the Eternal Self), lead us from Darkness (of Ignorance) to Light (of Spiritual Knowledge), lead us from the Fear of Death to the Knowledge of Immortality. Om Peace, Peace, Peace."

The universe and its creation is transcendental, and elevation of the soul is regarded as the ultimate truth behind such a creation. As a result, human beings tend to believe in the edification of this ultimate- the soul. The guru and the Acharya in the ancient times was considered as the custodian of this spiritual journey and intellectual discourses, since education cannot be compartmentalised. The teachers being the epitome of virtues helps one to move towards the known, unknown, finite, infinite, concrete, abstract, etc, and in this way dispels the darkness from life. The moment an individual undergoes this process of knowing the ultimate truth, s/he is bombarded with various questions about his/her existence, the creator, and the creation itself, and for the same reason s/he needs a mediator, and it is believed it is none other but the teacher, Acharya, or the Guru (*The Role of a Teacher in Spiritual Life, n.d.*). Here, the word Acharya, Guru, and Teacher has been used interchangeably in this article.

A teacher not only leads a student's spiritual journey, but also helps him/her unravel a path by teaching life skills, that is what an Acharya is well-known for (Nilachal, 2021). The Acharya leads towards the actual path of life and liberates one from the vicious cycle of ignorance. That's why teaching has been considered as a noble profession. However, various challenges have emerged, especially in the field of teaching, since the journey began from education 1.0 to the current education system 5.0. Undoubtedly, there are various factors behind this change, such as chronological power shifts, societal changes, cultural changes, and our eventual inability to hold on to the previous concept of teaching. Nevertheless, this paper will stick to the core notion of extracting the phenomenal qualities of an Acharya and find out whether the present teachers can incorporate some of these qualities.

Literature Review:

Academicians are critically introspecting the chronological order in the evolving notion of teachers with an interest in aligning it philosophically and culturally. Scholars have noted that the contemporary education system downplays teachers' professional independence, ethical perspectives, and cultural connotations. There has been a shift in teachers' role during the post-

independence period due to the increasing impact of state policies, which shaped the contemporary teacher education, creating incompetent teachers (Jain, 2016; Acharya and Swain, 2025). Additionally, teachers have been overburdened and marginalised nowadays, and hence their evolving roles and competencies are not promoted by the current system (Apat and Swain, 2023). Indeed, there is a sharp decline in the ethical standard among the teachers (Rawat et al., 2015), which is why the current education system has failed to instil the desired values among the future generation. Contrastingly, Banwala and Singh (2024), Rajguru (2024), and Adikari (2023) explored the ancient Gurukul education system and found that it was a student-focused and value-based approach, which could offer an alternative to today's colonial era-influenced consumerism and rote learning-based education system. Similarly, motivated by the teachings of the Bhagavad Gita, Hemalettha (2021) analysed the relevance of it in incorporating the ethical and emotional competencies among students through teachers. Finding the relevance of the Indian Knowledge System (IKS) which is the amalgamation of Sanatani texts including Veda, Vedangas, Upanishads, and Kala Vidya, Acharya (2024) and Devam and Joshi (2025) noted that integrating it with the contemporary system of education can help create culturally grounded, spiritually aware, and socially responsive educators.

In a nutshell, it can be stated that very few relevant research studies have been identified and hence cited, which has emphasised the role of ancient Acharyas with the present-day teachers. This literature review seeks to find the gaps and, hence, through this article, will redefine the notion of the modern education system, especially for teachers who would imbibe ancient values, morals, and spiritual awareness and enrichment.

Objectives

Therefore, this study has been conducted:

1. To explore whether there is any relevance of the ancient notion of a teacher, i.e., Acharya, among the present-day teachers.
2. To find out if the present-day teachers could adopt some qualities of an Acharya.

Methodology:

The study has been conducted utilising a qualitative approach by collecting and analysing information from secondary sources like the existing pieces of literature, news articles, renowned blog posts, and in some cases, personal communication.

Findings and Discussion:

This section has been divided into three segments, i.e., 1) exploring the qualities of an acharya existing in Ancient India, 2) finding out the present teachers' status, and 3) observing whether the impeccable qualities of the Acharya can be incorporated among the present-day teachers.

1. The Acharya:

The literal meaning of the word Acharya comprises of two words: 'A' meaning in the front, and 'Char' meaning to move or to demonstrate. Hence, one who moves or demonstrates from the front is called an Acharya. However, as per the ancient texts (source: uncertain):

"अचिनोति च शास्त्रार्थ आचरे प्रतिष्ठापयेत् ।

स्वयम् आचरते यस्मात् स आचार्यः अतिस्मृतः ॥"

"Achinoti cha shāstrārtham āchare pratiṣṭhāpayet |

Svayam ācharate yasmāt sa ācāryaḥ ati-smṛtaḥ ॥"

One who understands (Achinoti) the meaning of the scriptures (Shaastrartham), practices them, and establishes them in others (Aachare Pratishthaapayet), because he follows it himself (Svayam Aacharat), he is remembered (Ati Smritah) as a true teacher (Acharya) (Sa Acharyah) (Prajnannanda P.). In other words, the actual meaning of an Acharya would be a person who practices perfect behaviour, gives a perfect explanation of texts, picks up the true meaning of the scriptures, lives the way scriptures direct, and who can set an example for others to imbibe.

Therefore, s/he must walk the talk, possessing the utmost desired characteristics to be followed by others.

In ancient times, there was a sharp difference between the terms ‘shikshyak’, ‘acharya’, ‘guru’, and ‘sadguru’ (Nilachal, 2021). The difference is portrayed below in the form of a table:

Table 1: Differentiation of Teachers in Ancient India			
Shikshyak	Acharya	Guru	Sadguru
Teaches			
Art	Life skills	Consciousness	Merges with the universe by rising above self.
For			
Making the student holistically purna or complete.			

Therefore, the role of ancient teachers (‘shikshyak’ for teaching art, ‘acharya’ for teaching life skills, ‘guru’ for awakening consciousness, and ‘sadguru’ for teaching discipline) was to develop their students completely or holistically. However, in the understanding of this article, we will use these categories to denote a single concept: teachers in ancient times, i.e., Acharya. The ancient Indian education system was predominantly prevailing through the *Gurukul* model, which is believed to have originated as early as 5000 BCE (Adhikari, 2023). The term ‘Gurukul’ is itself a self-explanatory concept comprising ‘Guru’, meaning the Teacher, and ‘Kula’, meaning home or family. Therefore, a gurukul is a place where a shishya resided with their Guru or teacher. Most importantly, it used to be situated in remote places and sylvan surroundings, often near forests or mountains, so that the journey towards attainment would be peaceful and serene (Rajguru N. 2024). Hence, it is quite evident that the environmentally serene places were prioritised in ancient times as far as the surrounding environment of the institution was concerned.

The relationship between guru and shishya was of prominent importance in the ancient education system. Adhikari T. N. (2023) mentioned that the way a mother carries her child in her womb, a student is welcomed at a Gurukul. That means they had a symbiotic relationship, which Acharya S. (2024) described as a reflective bond between the two that helped them create the base for effective learning and personal growth. Their relationship was based on mutual respect, trust, and spiritual guidance (Rajguru N. 2024). According to Rajguru N. (2024), the guru was the spiritual guide, mentor, and role model to the shishya. Likewise, a shishya had to show complete devotion, discipline, and reverence for the guru or Acharya, which laid the foundation of their spiritual relationship. A shishya would consider his/her guru or Acharya as a spiritual figure. They would chant “Guru Brahma, Guru Vishnu, Guru Devo Maheswara” (i.e., guru is brahma, vishnu, and devo maheswara signifying the trinity of creation, Copyright@2025 Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science & English Language

preservation, and destruction). In a nutshell, the relation between them was completely pure, true, ethical, and devotional.

Spiritual learning of the shishya was considered as godly in the ancient education system. Hence, the god-seeking qualities of the students were of utmost importance to the Acharya. In ancient texts like Chandogya Upanishads, Mukunda Upanishad, and Brihadaranaka Upanishad, the importance of a true God-seeker, shishya, has been prioritised. *The Role of a Teacher in Spiritual Life* (n.d) argued that when someone is ready for the journey in terms of God-seeking, it would be easy for the teacher to show them the actual path in life. The instance of Swami Vivekananda and Ramakrishna is quite citable here, because when Vivekananda inquired whether Ramakrishna saw God, and in reply, he said, “Yes, my boy. I have seen God. I see God clearer than I see you. And if you are eager, I can help you see God.” In other words, the teachers’ job used to be teaching spiritual learning as well. When Aristotle said, “Educating the mind, without educating the heart is no education at all” (as quoted in Sardar, 2018), it simply implies that students are expected to develop emotionally, ethically, morally, and spiritually. Additionally, students would go *to collect alms in return*. They would collect firewood for sacrificial fire, a tradition in the ashrama (*The Role of a Teacher in Spiritual Life*, n.d.).

The concept of monetary payoffs was not there in our ancient education system (Adhikari T. N. 2023). At the age of 8-12 years, the shishyas would enter the gurukul, and they would exit it at the age of 25 years. During this whole journey, the students wouldn’t pay any fees. Most importantly, they didn’t have to pay it. Only they had to repay by offering Gurudakshina or alms to the Acharya, and sometimes it would be in the form of making commitments like lifelong service, fulfilling a moral duty, or completing a specific task entrusted by the guru (Sharma, 2015; Radhakrishnan, 2009). These acts were seen not as economic transactions but as gestures of gratitude and respect. It reflects how educators in ancient times prioritized developing their students’ competence over pursuing materialistic personal gain.

The all-around development of the shishya was the priority of our ancient education system. The acharya would develop his/her shishya academically, physically, mentally, and spiritually (Adhikari T. N. 2023). Academic subjects like the Vedas, Philosophy, or logic were taught to the students. They took part in practising meditation and spiritual practices. They were expected to imbibe moral values and norms for ethical conduct. They were also instructed to develop necessary life skills. For instance, as per Hemalettha (2021), Lord Krishna helped Arjuna develop necessary life skills like problem-solving, self-awareness, decision-making,

coping with emotions, and interpersonal communication while he was in mental conflict on the battlefield of Kurukshetra.

During ancient education, the mindset and the temperament of the Acharya played a pivotal role. It was often observed that they waited patiently for the right disciple to start specific discourse. The arrival of Rishi Valmiki to King Dasharatha asking Ram and Laxman to be his shishya (Nilachal, 2021), portrayed the same.

Because of all these factors, the Acharya in the ancient education system was respected by everybody in the society. According to Aristotle, “Those who educate the child are more honoured than their parents because parents give them life, but teachers give them the art of living.” The two epics, Mahabharata and Ramayana, placed teachers on the highest pedestal (Gupta, 2019). Being completely disarmed, an emperor would pay visits to the Acharya. Additionally, the way a king received his guru in the court also reflected the respect a teacher commanded during ancient times. Hence, all these qualities of an Acharya resonate with the true definition that has been elaborated earlier in the Sanskrit quotation.

In a nutshell, the qualities of an Acharya can be demonstrated in the following chart:

2. Status of the Present Teachers:

The intervention of various intruders changed the cultural trajectory of the Indian education system. It was quite intensified during the British colonial period in India. Various British policies played a crucial role in this cultural transformation. Adikari T. N. (2023) argued that Macaulay’s Minute (1835) changed the traditional Indian education system into the Western model of institutions. Hence, it is quite evident that the intervention of the Britishers has changed the trajectory of the Indian Education System (Banwala & Singh, 2024; Devam &

Joshi, 2025; & Apat & Swain, 2023). In the contemporary context, teachers have started deviating from their ethical and moral standards. There are various factors behind such an assumption.

The future of a generation depends upon teachers. Those who teach the future generation, if not trained well, will obstruct the destiny of the upcoming generation. For this reason, the need for teacher education is indispensable. Teacher education is nothing but the combination of teaching skills, pedagogical theory, and professional skills (Samaddar & Khatun, 2024). The Indian government has various teachers' training programs from the very beginning, starting from in-service (Refresher Sources, FIP, & FDP) to pre-service (D.El.Ed., B.Ed., & M.Ed.) teacher training programs. However, the question is whether teachers have developed enough resilience and competencies for this noble profession.

With the introduction of such training programs, there is a growing trend for making this segment (D.El.Ed/B.Ed/M.Ed) market-oriented. Researchers like Nambissan (2020) and Tilak (2015) argued that the rapidly rising demand for education has spurred the entry of private players, shifting schooling towards a consumer-centric model. In this shift, foundational elements vital for quality education—such as adequate funding, infrastructure, and trained teachers—are often compromised or overlooked. Eventually, there is a downtrend in terms of maintaining the qualities of a teacher that hampers the overall education system. Once they come to this profession with inadequate competencies, they try to treat it materialistically. As Apat and Swain (2023) argued, they think of commodifying their knowledge and skills they have possessed and becoming entrepreneurs in light of today's neoliberal market. Hence, education has become a booming industry, and instead of truly teaching them, teachers have become service providers, and students have become consumers (Joshi et al., 2015). Consequently, education is increasingly seen as a market transaction. This shift reflects a significant transformation in the perception of teaching—from a value-based vocation to a commercial enterprise. Unlike historical contexts where educators sought only voluntary offerings or *dakshina*, the contemporary trend treats teaching as a business venture (personal communication, 2025).

Teachers should dedicate themselves to develop the students holistically. However, in the contemporary context, it can be observed that only the academics of the students, i.e., their academic parameters of degrees, are focused on, neglecting their emotional and ethical development (personal communication, 2025). Hence, there is a growing trend of mental health

issues. It's quite visible when students commit suicide, as their expectations are not met on a specific examination. A recent example of a Gurgaon-based 17-year-old boy's suicide because of his underperformance made this assumption very clear (PTI, 2025). That means the present education system is failing to meet the well-being of the students. Additionally, there is a sharp decline in the ethical conduct of the students. For example, Al Jazeera (2020) reported on the nefarious plan of 'Bois locker room' incident in Delhi ("*Bois Locker Room*": *Indian Teen Probed over Instagram Rape Chats*, 2020), wherein a group of minor students of Class XI and XII were planning to rape and assault women. Such incidents are nothing but a portrayal of the current degradation of the students' ethical approach. They are not influenced by the teachers anymore. Teachers are also booked for sexual harassment in some cases. The recent Mumbai incident portrays the same, wherein a 40 year old teacher was charged with POCSO Act for assaulting a 16 year old school girl (Suresh, 2025). However, the contemporary education system is least bothered about such degeneration.

Earlier, the spiritual development of the students was of utmost importance to the Acharya. However, in the contemporary context, there is no such importance provided for the spiritual development of the students on the real ground. Students are also turning out to be a market-driven product, just like teachers, a state servant or service provider, wherein the material life matters to them quite a lot. They hardly think of self-reflection, contemplation, and meditation; rather, they would go to any extent to be restless, having a mind full of materialistic lusts (personal communication, 2025). Hence, the high-salary-driven teachers can hardly think of shaping students spiritually.

A teacher is expected to be an ideal person to be followed by society. However, teachers are not setting a positive example in today's context. They are found to be very lenient with the students. Sometimes, it crosses all boundaries. Take the recent example of a professor found marrying her student in one of the state aided universities of West Bengal ("*Classroom 'Wedding' with Student Puts West Bengal College Professor in a Spot - Times of India*," 2025) is a real whistle-blower that it is the time to restore the position of the teachers in our society. They are also found to be guilty of bribing the authority in terms of securing their job position in the merit lists (Sengupta, 2024).

With modern inventions like artificial intelligence, the challenges in the teaching profession have started increasing. Generally, it has been observed that an obsessive inclination towards genitive AI has impacted brain health gravely. Moreover, it leads to reduced use of the

hippocampus, disrupting alpha brain waves, and eventually contributing to dementia. Additionally, it minimises creativity. Therefore, despite its positive aspects, like feasibility in teaching, the moment teachers take stride with generative artificial intelligence (AI) like ChatGPT in their teaching, they start compromising negatively on the ethics of the teaching profession (Tripathi Puja et al., 2025). This has resulted in a deviation from the novelty in teaching due to the casual and often use of AI. Furthermore, this leads teachers towards holding a mechanical outlook rather than a humanistic touch in their profession. The European Union has already considered education at high risk due to AI (*Use of AI in Education: Deciding on the Future We Want*, 2024).

A bird's eye view of the status of past & present teachers

In a nutshell, these are the factors that speak highly of the demand for cultural consciousness to be incorporated among the teachers. Since teachers are the backbone of the education

system, they can incorporate the highly desired values among the future generation, which will act as a backbone for a better society.

On the same note, it is essential to view what our prominent educationists have to say about teachers. Swami Vivekananda considered a teacher a non-ignorant, conscious soul who will develop another conscious soul (Dutta, 2019). He has prioritised the divine characteristics of a teacher who would possess a strong personality. Additionally, with the purpose of aesthetic and moral development of the students, Sri Aurobindo wanted his integral education to be spiritually meaningful (Pal, 2019). This means the pioneers in the field of education have also emphasised the importance of spirituality in the contemporary education context. If this assumption of spirituality for the teachers and students is fulfilled, then only the notion that an awakened mind can lighten up another mind will be proven.

3. Qualities of Acharya needed to be incorporated among the Present Teachers:

The Acharya is a Sanatani concept that has ingrained its stem and is deeply rooted into Indian culture from ancient times. However, despite facing backlash, the current government has shown its strength in restoring the lost culture through various ways. P.M. Modi has said, “Mother gives birth, teachers give life”. That rightfully resonates with the concept of an ideal teacher. As per Gupta (2019), an ideal teacher is not a subject teacher who only teaches content to his/her students, but also ignites the spark of curiosity in the mind of a student. He will be an Acharya who will become a role model by walking the talk and teaching life skills as well as moral values. He will be a guru by driving students out of darkness through lighting up lights and portraying how bliss, a sense of completeness, and fulfilment can be achieved. Moreover, he will empower minds.

He will be reluctant to consider education as a market-driven concept; rather, he will actively take part in restoring the honour of teachers. The National Education Policy (NPE 2020) also mentioned that respect for teachers and the teaching profession should be reestablished (Ministry of Human Resource Development, 2020). He will consider teaching a noble profession since teaching, as per Ulferts (2021), is the mother of all professions. He will maintain a healthy relationship with students. He will be as flexible as the Acharya so that he can accommodate the present requirements of the society. He will not only be an expert in the field but also teach life skills to the students. He will also be inclined towards the spiritual development of the students to realise the pillars of the Delors Commission: learning to be, and learning to live together.

Post-independence India witnessed several commissions and committees that laid the foundation for teacher development and educational reforms. The University Education Commission (1948–49), chaired by Dr. S. Radhakrishnan, emphasized the moral and professional integrity of teachers as nation-builders. This was followed by the Secondary Education Commission (1952–53), led by Dr. A. Lakshmanswamy Mudaliar, which underscored the need for well-trained secondary school teachers. The Education Commission (1964–66), under Dr. D.S. Kothari, advocated for a common school system and recommended professionalisation of teacher education with a national policy framework. The National Policy on Education (1986) and its 1992 revision institutionalised teacher training through District Institutes of Education and Training (DIETs) and stressed continuous professional development. More recently, the National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education (NCFTE, 2009) and the recommendations of the NEP 2020 have focused attention on holistic teacher preparation, quality assurance, and integration of Indian knowledge systems. These policy shifts reflect a consistent recognition of teachers as central agents in achieving equitable and quality education.

The present central government is truly proactive in this direction. They have oriented the NPE 2020 and talked about the Indian Knowledge System (IKS). IKS is the enriched bowl of our ancient knowledge, comprising of Vedas, upvedas, vedangas, and other kalas (technically known as paravidya and aparavidya) that were taught to the ancient shishyas and accordingly imbibe the high moral, ethical, spiritual, and emotional values for life-leading purpose. Accordingly, the University Grants Commission has published guidelines for incorporating IKS for at least 5% of the total mandated credits of Undergraduate and Post-Graduate students (Acharya, 2024; *Guidelines for Incorporating Indian Knowledge in Higher Education Curricula*, 2023). Additionally, they have taken various initiatives to promote IKS and make them 21st-century skill-ready. A national mission for improving the learning outcomes of elementary-level students has been launched through an integrated teacher training program called NISHTHA under the Samagra Shiksha scheme of 2019-2020 (*NISHTHA: National Initiative for School Heads' Teachers' Holistic Advancement*, 2019). Moreover, they have come up with the platforms of SWAYAM and SWAYAM PLUS for increasing the accessibility of quality resourced education, as well as Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana (PMKVY) under the Skill India program for upskilling the youth (“Indian Government Initiatives to Upskill the Nation and Its Youth,” 2024). Against this backdrop, by introducing the National Curriculum

Framework for School Education, followed by NPE 2020, they have tried to make a connection between 21st-century demands and the IKS through such endeavours (Chaturvedi, 2024). Therefore, it can be interpreted that such an optimistic attitude of the government will be beneficial for incorporating the values related to the lost notion of the ancient heritage of India, i.e., its culture, education, teaching, and overall teachers among the present generation.

Additionally, the notion 'Education 5.0' has been reverberated in NPE 2020, wherein education is expected to be modern technology-driven and at the same time has to be embedded in promoting values. Teachers are expected to be aligned with cultural values as well as modern challenges. It is quintessential that teachers then can be regarded as the facilitators, mentors, and co-creators of knowledge.

Conclusion:

The contextual transition has been so rapid that it has caused dent to the educational system. The same has happened with our culture, i.e., we are unable to get hold of the legacy transmitted by our Acharya. As a result, there has been a sharp decline in the present status of teachers, despite their role as the rightful front runner of the ancient ideal of an Acharya. However, in the present context, it can be illustrated that Acharya was not only responsible for imparting knowledge and teaching life skills to the students, but also for the overall well-being and development of the students. Since the government is quite proactive in terms of incorporating such ideals through IKS, it can be predicted that a bright tomorrow is waiting for us in terms of reviving the lost culture related to a teacher or the teaching profession. For this reason, we need to embed this notion of an Acharya among the present generation through our education system, i.e., teacher training programs, so that there can be a cultural reawakening among them. In this context, more strategies need to be developed to realise the vision of Viksit Bharat 2047" as teachers are the backbone of a society.

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